

Institute of Power Engineering
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CFD EVALUATION OF THE OXY-FUEL TECHNOLOGY APPLIED TO ROTARY CEMENT KILN

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Rotary cement kiln conditions

- 1 - Kiln inlet
- 2 - Rotary tube
- 3 - Tyre with tyre attachment system
- 4 - Kiln hood
- 5 - Main burner
- 6 - Kiln outlet

Illustrative drawing of the rotary kiln

75 MW cement kiln burner

Composition of the meal fed to the kiln during the process of clinker formation

CFD model setup

Ansys Fluent was used for CFD computations:

- steady state flow of incompressible viscous fluid composed of species mixture,
- turbulence model k-omega GEKO,
- chemical reactions, model FR-ED for the reaction rate,
- discrete ordinates method for radiation modeling,
- solid fuels modelled by the DPM model,
- boundary conditions determined by the actual operating conditions of the kiln.

Cases	petcoke flow, kg/s	RDF flow, kg/s	H ₂ flow, kg/s	RDF share, %	H ₂ share, %
100% petcoke	2.197	0	0	0	0
100% RDF	0	2.574	0	100	0
40% petcoke, 60% RDF	0.888	1.538	0	60	0
5% H ₂ , 95%RDF	0	2.446	0.0312	95	5.0
10% H ₂ , 90%RDF	0	2.317	0.0625	90	10.0

Starting scenarios (cases)

Comparison of temperature profiles

- Combustion of 100% RDF is not feasible
- Min. share of petcoke is 40%_{en.}
- In 95/5 RDF/H₂ case there is a significant ignition delay increase
- In 90/10 RDF/H₂ case the ignition begins very close to the burner

Starting cases – axis temperature profile

- 100% RDF – very low temperatures up to 15m after the burner outlet – ignition and combustion issues
- 95/5% RDF/H₂ – slightly better than above, but still not sufficient
- 90/10% RDF/H₂ – much faster ignition, better profile, but high temperature peak – risk of infrastructure damage

Maybe oxy-fuel combustion is the solution?

- oxygen addition increases combustion temperature
- oxygen is the by-product of water electrolysis
- full oxy-fuel mode is not feasible with electrolysis due to the production limitations: $8\text{kgO}_2/1\text{kgH}_2$ (O_2 concentration in the primary air is $26.3\%_{\text{vol.}}$)

40% petcoke with 60% RDF (reference case 2)

95/5% RDF/H₂ + partial oxy-fuel mode

Maybe oxidizer heating-up will help?

- the increased oxidizer temperature helps the ignition
- it is quite straight-forward in terms of the primary oxidizer
- there are materials and equipment limitations (max. temp. ~ 300 °C)

40% petcoke with 60% RDF (reference case 2)

95/5% RDF/H2 + partial oxy-fuel mode, oxidizer=100 °C

95/5% RDF/H2 + partial oxy-fuel mode, oxidizer=300 °C

H2 injection strategy

- instead injecting the H₂ through the dedicated inlet injection together with RDF?
- improved mixing and ignition?
- safety issues?

Final cases – axis temperature profile

- 93/7% RDF/H₂ is the closest case to the base-case one
- partial oxy-fuel mode doesn't help
- neither the oxidizer (mild) heating
- neither the additional H₂ injection with RDF

Techno-economic analysis

- 3 cases analysed:
 - case 1: own production (and storage) of H₂ (electricity from the grid)
 - case 2: own production (and storage) of H₂ (full PV + full BESS)
 - case 3: purchasing the H₂ on the "market"
- assumptions (between 2026 – 2035):
 - pet-coke cost: 132.5 €/t (4.42 €/GJ)
 - H₂ cost: 4.5 – 1.7 €/kg
 - EUA cost: 82 – 195 €/t
 - Electricity cost: 190 €/MWh (~ const.)
 - RDF cost: 0.83 €/GJ (~ const.)
 - PV: 60 MWp
 - BESS: 200 MWh
 - electricity cost kills the enterprise
 - other viable option could be full PV + back-up BESS + PPA + SOE
 - subsidies can significantly reduce CAPEX and improve economy
- results:
 - case 1: NPV: -32mln €, IRR: -37%
 - case 2: NPV: -40mln €, IRR: -4%
 - case 3: NPV: 45mln €, IRR: 106%

Summary

- Due to high content of moisture, non-homogeneities, highly variable PSD, RDF is not recommended to combust as a sole fuel in the rotary cement kiln.
- The hydrogen addition to the fuel mixture can improve the combustion behaviour in the standard burner, but the hydrogen share should be in the range 5-10%_{en}.
- The optimized for analysed burner hydrogen share is 7%_{en}.
- As previous studies showed it is necessary to reach 27-33%vol. of O₂ in the oxidizer and ~20% of FGR to achieve proper kiln temperatures. These require high-output ASU and FGR system.
- Moreover, oxy-fuel, to be effective, requires limited false air ingress to control combustion atmosphere.
- As usual, the ASU is the main source of cost – it can increase the electricity demand by up to ~140%.
- Assuming the maturity of the hydrogen value chain and predicted costs, even co-firing 7%_{en} of hydrogen can be economically feasible.

Thank you!

Q&A

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